

Adsorption of Carbon Dioxide at 273°K on Hydrogels, Clay Minerals and Soils and Evaluation of Surface Area by Using Dubinin Equation

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Specific surface areas of a few microporous systems (hydrogels, clay minerals and soils) as obtained from (i) carbon dioxide adsorption isotherms (273°K) by applying Dubinin equation, (ii) nitrogen adsorption isotherms (77°K) by applying B.E.T. equation, (iii) water adsorption isotherms (298°K) by applying Harkins-Jura equation (in the case of hydrogels only), and (iv) glycol retention technique have been determined. The data indicate that while nitrogen molecules at 77°K can diffuse through the micropores in the case of hydrogels, they cannot do so effectively in the case of clays and soils. Carbon dioxide, due to its higher critical temperature, can be used at a much higher temperature and its molecules at 273°K seem to have sufficient kinetic energy to diffuse effectively in all cases except montmorillonite clays.

ADSORPTION of carbon dioxide at temperatures around 273°K has been used in recent years for estimating surface areas of a variety of carbons including coals¹⁻³, anthracites^{4,5}, activated carbons^{6,7}, carbon blacks^{7,8} and carbon molecular sieves⁹ by applying Dubinin-Polanyi equation¹⁰. The widely used B.E.T. method is not regarded suitable in the case of microporous solids since adsorption of nitrogen at such a low temperature as 77°K is limited by activated diffusion of the gas through the micropores and an appreciable proportion of the internal surface remains inaccessible to the gas¹¹. Carbon dioxide has a higher critical temperature (~ 304°K) and, therefore, can be used at a higher temperature. Anderson, Bayer and Hofer¹¹ have shown that a part of the internal surface in coals which is inaccessible to nitrogen at 77°K is accessible to carbon dioxide at 195°K even though molecular area of carbon dioxide (17 Å²) is slightly higher than that of nitrogen (16.2 Å²). Adsorption of carbon dioxide at 273°K is usually recommended. As the saturation vapour pressure (P_s) of carbon dioxide at this temperature is of the order of 34 atmospheres, the relative vapour pressure (P/P_s) along the isotherm remains very low. In this range of relative vapour pressure Dubinin-Polanyi (D-P) equation and not B.E.T. equation is applicable. The perusal of the literature shows that carbon dioxide adsorption at 273°K, as interpreted in the light of D-P equation, has not been used for estimating surface areas of hydrogels or clays and soils in all of which surface area is an important single value factor for their characterisation.

Experimental

Silica gel (N.C.L. Batch No. 0871), alumina gel (B.D.H., C.P.), seven clay minerals received as gift

from I.A.R.I., New Delhi through the courtesy of Dr. B. Ramamoorthy, and two soil samples were used in the present investigations. Adsorption of carbon dioxide (prepared by the action of dilute HCl (A.R.) on CaCO₃ (A.R.) and dried by passing through calcium chloride columns and of 99.8 per cent. purity) was studied volumetrically at 273°K, using a self-fabricated equipment after the well known B.E.T. apparatus. Equilibrium was attained within 40-45 min. at each pressure. Adsorption of nitrogen at 77°K was also determined on the same apparatus in the same manner. Liquid nitrogen was obtained from the Nangal Fertiliser Plant at Nangal. The saturation pressure (P_s) of CO₂ at 273°K was taken as 34.4 atmospheres while that of N₂ at 77°K was taken as 1 atmosphere. Adsorption of water vapour was studied at 298°K in the case of silica and alumina gels by using McBain's balance technique.

Specific surface areas were calculated by applying D-P equation to adsorption isotherms of carbon dioxide, and B.E.T. equation to adsorption isotherms of nitrogen. Surface areas of silica and alumina gels were also calculated from their water isotherms by using Harkins-Jura equation, as had been done by Orchiston¹² and Puri and Sharma¹³. Surface areas of soils and clays were also obtained by the glycol retention method proposed by Dyal and Hendricks¹⁴ and used widely for this purpose in such systems.

Results and Discussion

According to D-P equation, which is intended to describe adsorption in microporous systems.

$$\log V = \log V_0 - D(\log P_s/p)^2$$

where V is the volume of carbon dioxide adsorbed at equilibrium pressure P, V_0 is micropore capacity, P_s is saturation pressure of the gas, and, $D=K/\beta^2$, where K is a constant at a given temperature while β is the affinity coefficient of the adsorbate.

The plots of $(\log P_s/p)^2$ against $\log V$ for some of the adsorbents, as shown in Figure 1, are linear,

Fig. 1. Dubinin plots of CO_2 isotherms (273°K) on a few porous adsorbents (○—○ Silica gel, Δ—Δ Alumina gel, ×—× Illite, □—□ Montmorillonite, ▲—▲ Halloysite, ■—■ Soil No. 2).

indicating applicability of the equation to our data. The plots for the rest of the samples were also similar and have not been given for reasons of space. The intercepts of the linear plots at $(\log P_s/P)^2=0$ give the respective values of V_0 from which the respective surface areas could be calculated knowing the molecular area of carbon dioxide to be 17Å^2 . This area may be taken as accessible to carbon

dioxide molecules through pore entrances of width $< 4.2 \text{Å}$ (molecular thickness of CO_2). The results are given in Table 1.

Fig. 2. B. E. T. plots for the adsorption of nitrogen (77°K) on a few porous adsorbents (Δ—Δ Alumina gel, ×—× Illite, ▲—▲ Halloysite, □—□ Soil No. 2, ○—○ Vermiculite).

The B.E.T. plots of nitrogen at 77°K for some of the adsorbents are shown in Figure 2. The values of V_m , as obtained from the intercepts and slopes of these plots in the usual manner, and the surface area values calculated by taking molecular area of nitrogen as 16.2Å^2 are included in Table 1.

The Harkins-Jura plots for adsorption of water vapour at 298°K by silica and alumina gels are linear (Fig. 3), as expected. The values of surface area (S) obtained from the slopes (A) of the plots by employing the expression

$$S = K \times A^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

and taking the value of the constant K as $38.3^{1/2}$ are

TABLE—1 SURFACE AREAS OF POROUS ADSORBENTS AS OBTAINED BY DIFFERENT METHODS

Adsorbent	By adsorption of nitrogen (77°K ; B.E.T.)		By adsorption of CO_2 (273°K ; D-P) equation		By water adsorption isotherms (298°K)		By glycol retention method	
	V_m (cm^3 (STP)/g)	Surface area (m^2 /g)	V_0 (cm^3 (STP)/g)	Surface area (m^2 /g)	Slope of H.J. plot	Surface area (m^2 /g)	Amount of glycol retained (mg/g)	Surface area (m^2 /g)
Silica gel	66.57	290	57.53	263	58.90	294	—	—
Alumina gel	28.56	124	20.35	93	10.99	127	—	—
Soil No. 1	1.38	6	5.91	27	—	—	8.1	26
Soil No. 2	2.60	11	7.87	36	—	—	12.4	40
Kaolin	6.43	28	7.44	34	—	—	9.3	30
Vermiculite	1.84	8	5.47	25	—	—	13.3	43
Illite	15.75	69	18.16	83	—	—	33.8	109
Pyrophyllite	1.15	5	9.63	44	—	—	18.0	58
Chlorite	1.15	5	5.91	27	—	—	13.3	43
Halloysite	7.49	33	17.94	82	—	—	32.9	106
Montmorillonite	4.14	18	14.44	66	—	—	79.4	256

also given in Table 1. The surface areas of clay minerals and soils obtained from glycol retention method are also included in the Table for easy comparison.

Fig. 3. Harkins-Jura plots for adsorption of water vapour (298°K) by Silica (O—O) and Alumina (●—●) gels.

It is seen, in the first place, that the values for silica and alumina gels, as obtained by the B.E.T. technique, are fairly close to those obtained from water isotherms. As is well known these gels consist generally of open pores of cylindrical shape. It appears, therefore, that nitrogen molecules can diffuse through the system fairly well and most of the internal surface becomes accessible even at 77°K. The values obtained from the adsorption of carbon dioxide at the higher temperature of 273°K, by applying D-P equation, are, in fact, relatively smaller. This may be explained as due to slightly higher molecular area of carbon dioxide. In any case, the objection to the B.E.T. technique, on account of low rate of diffusion of nitrogen at 77°K, does not appear to be valid in the case of silica and alumina hydrogel systems.

As regards the soils and clay minerals, leaving montmorillonite aside for the present, it is seen that the CO₂ values are invariably higher than the nitrogen values. It appears that in these microporous systems, nitrogen at 77°K does not diffuse fully into the minute capillary pores while carbon dioxide at 273°K has sufficient kinetic energy to penetrate into them and hence a part of the surface inaccessible to nitrogen at the lower temperature becomes accessible to carbon dioxide at the higher temperature. The values obtained from glycol retention in the case of kaolin, which has an open

structure, as well as the soils, are seen to be fairly close to those obtained from CO₂-isotherms. But in the case of the rest of the clay minerals, the values from glycol retention are comparatively higher. This may be, in part at least, due to difference in the nature of forces involved. There may be some specific interaction of the hydrogen bonding type between —OH groups of glycol with the oxy- and oxy-hydrogen groups of soils and clays. In fact the method based on glycol retention may not be free from this possible objection. The use of carbon dioxide as an adsorbate at 273°K may provide a more suitable method for estimating surface areas of such systems.

It is in the case of montmorillonite that the carbon dioxide value, though appreciably higher than the nitrogen value, is considerably lower than the result obtained from the glycol retention method. Montmorillonite is an expanding lattice type of clay. When a substance like water, methanol or glycol enters between the ultimate sheets, it causes swelling and also separation of lamellae and therefore gets adsorbed and imbibed into the very interior of the system, as has been pointed out by Mooney, Keenan and Wood¹⁵ as well as Nelson and Hendricks¹⁶. It is doubtful if a non-polar gas like carbon dioxide can diffuse through the very minute pores within the adhering sheets to give a complete coverage of the internal surface.

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